

Building a Sustainable Joint between Rural and Urban Areas through Circular and Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains

 D1.1

European forests as raw material supplier in the construction sector

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Executive summary

WP1 defines the context in which the BASAJAUN project will address construction processes in connection with sustainable regional development.

The main objectives of WP1 are:

- analysing the potential of European forests as a sustainable supplier of raw material for wood-based construction.
- analysing building with wood as a sustainable development driver in rural areas.
- exploiting synergies between rural and urban areas through the integration of resources and demands considering technical and socioeconomic aspects.
- overcoming technical, administrative, financial and social barriers to extend the market for wood in construction.
- analysing current and defining future wood construction value chains.

The forest policies in relation to construction materials supplies and compiled to show the different approaches will be mapped and analysed in some countries that participate in the project (Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Poland, Sweden, Finland and Chile).

This deliverable D1.1 is a document of the BASAJAUN project, provided in the context of WP1 -Task T1.1: European forests as a raw material supplier in the construction sector.

D1.1 is focused in:

- species used mainly for construction purposes in terms of quality of trees and timber, harvesting methods considering stand density and rotation;
- market models (harvesting scenario, timber dimension and quality requirements, etc.)
- localisation – distance from end- markets in urban areas and sawmills or other transformation facilities both within and between countries. Panel and board products are also part of the wood construction sector. For simplification only sawn timber products had been used for the modelling in BASAJAUN project. A French case study has been used. EN standards and other national regulations for trading of roundwood and sawn-timber products applied in construction can affect the results estimated with this approach.
- models describing qualities of trees and timber are summarized to show the desired tree characteristics to produce generic raw materials and products.
- quantify the actual supply of wood for construction and estimate the potential for the next 10 years.
- a review of the latest traceability tools (reading input, integrating parameters, marking of output) will be done for tree assessment and will be further used in WP3 D3-1.

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Glossary

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Full term</i>
C24	One of strength classes from EN 338
CE	Conformité Européenne
CLT	Cross Laminated Timber
D	Deliverable
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
EN	European standard
GA	Grant Agreement
G4-1	One of aesthetic softwood grade from EN1611-1
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
RFID	Radio-frequency Identification
ROI	Return of Investment
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Forests and other wood land represent around 44% of the EU's surface. This area has seen continual growth over the last 50 years and the four regions of European woodland (the majority are boreal; along with central; alpine; and Mediterranean types of forest) represent 5% of the world's forests [Probst 2016].

While forest land can be found across all of Europe, the greatest concentrations of woodland are boreal forests (found in Northern European countries).

Figure 1 Coverage of forest land across Europe [Kempeneers 2012].

Over the last 50 years, forest area and the standing timber volume has seen a significant growth as shown by the EUROSTAT data [EUROSTAT 2015]. The analysis of this information (Table 1) made it possible to quantify relevant parameters making it possible to understand the productivity of the forest:

- the annual volume of trees harvested is less than the annual production in the majority of forest areas in Europe, the potential to increase harvest while keeping the sustainability of forest management is a reality
- silvicultural work generates 800 rural jobs per 1000 m³ (forest to log yard) in some European regions,
- one rural job in sawmill provide 486 m³ of sawn timber.

Table 1. Evaluation of European forest potential in 2015

Forest	EUROPEAN UNION [EU28]
Forest and other wooded land area	182 M ha (42% of land area)
Growing stock of forests * (A)	26534 M m3 (hardwood = 11197; Softwood = 15337)
Net annual increment in forests available for wood supply (2010) (B)	744.2 M m3(hardwood = 314.1; Softwood = 430.1)
ratio (B/A)	2.8%
• Annual increment (%)	
ratio (B/A) for hardwood	2.8%
ratio (B/A) for softwood	2.8%
Roundwood removals (C)	472.642 M m3
Ratio (C/A)	1.8%
•	
Industrial roundwood removals	351.201 M m3
Employment in forestry and logging (D)	536.5 thou.
Percentage of female workers in forestry and logging (Percentage of female workers in forestry and forest based industry - 20,0%)	13,3%
Ratio (C/D)	881
• number of employed in forestry and logging to produce 1 m ³ of roundwood	
Sawn-wood production (E)	104,814 M m3
Employment in manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials(F)	1016,2 thous.
Ratio (F/E)	0,01
• sawn-wood production (m ³) per employed	

* basing on the growing stock in forest in European Union countries in 2015, Forestry, 2017, Central Statistical Office, Warszawa, 2017, p. 304: hardwood – 42,2%, softwood – 57,8%

Source: Eurostat data base; FAOSTAT data base; Forestry, 2017, Central Statistical Office, Warszawa, 2017, p. 304.

Wood is a renewable resource, but it needs to be managed sustainably. The annual volume of roundwood harvested needs to be less than the annual production that sequesters carbon-dioxide from the atmosphere in a process of photosynthesis. Using the photonic energy of sunlight as a fuel, the chloroplast in needles and leaves turns approximately 800 kg of atmospheric CO₂ and soil water into carbon hydrates, from which the tree's cambium makes one cubic metre of lignocellulosic cell wall. The exhaust gas of the process (700 kg of oxygen) is released to the atmosphere. In addition to human activities, the volume of standing trees could be affected by natural hazards, such as wildfires, storms, and insect outbreaks. In such case, the volume of standing trees can change in a matter of hours or days.

The typical products made of harvested round wood in first transformation processes consist of industrial roundwood, sawnwood, veneers, wood-based panels and wood fuels. Wood products can be reused, recycled or incinerated with the energy recovery at the end of their lifecycle, just like other forest biomasses that are unsuitable for processing. Once harvested, wood is sawmilled or otherwise processed to produce staple products of the forest industry such as pulp, paper, board products, paper goods and packaging. These goods serve to meet the demands of industries such as construction, carpentry, furniture and biomass, biofuel refining, textiles and many more applications.

The forest-based industries [Probst L 2016] constitute one of EU's largest industrial sectors, accounting for around 10% of total value of manufacturing production, value-added and employment. The forest products market grew by 1.3% in 2013 to reach a value of 110 billion euros and a volume of around 695.5 million m³. By 2018, it reached a value of around 129 billion euros. There are approximately 456,000 companies operating in the sector today.

European forest-based industries provide employment and income for some 2.6 million people directly all over the EU, in particular in remote areas, and help the EU's 16 million private forest owners generate economic growth, while contributing to enhance biodiversity and to tackle climate change.

At this part of the BASAJAUN project, an analysis is carried out whether the volume of the trees is enough to satisfy the demands of an increasing wooden construction market and to optimise value chains of wooden industries. A balanced way based on the compromise between the appropriate wood in the right place and the increasing rural employment simultaneously.

The allocation of suitable materials to mills, processes and products is crucial for the sustainability of the forestry-wood chains. All aspects of sustainability must be taken into account: environmental, economics and societal. If less suitable material is allocated to a process, this will normally lead to losses in yield and value. The processing will be less efficient, with use of more material, energy, etc. than necessary per unit produced. Less suitable materials may have to be redirected to other processes or mills, which means more transportation costs. In addition, the quality, product functionality and customer satisfaction may be negatively affected.

2. Trees used for construction – BASAJAUN Case study

As shown in Table 1, European wood-based industries can increase its raw material sourcing in a sustainable way which could additionally improve production processes to answer to the demand of markets. Therefore, an analysis of key figures had been carefully carried out. Some information was missing to describe the full "transformation" chain.

The wood production efficiency was mapped and analysed in some of the most representative countries that participate in the project (Finland, France, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden) in relation to construction materials supplies and it was compiled to show the different approaches in terms of:

- number of employees to produce 1000 m³ of harvested roundwood and
- volume of sawtimber (m³) produced by employee

Figure 2 shows the evaluation of those parameters obtained from the analyse of EUROSTAT data per BASAJAUN partners countries.

Figure 2 Evolution of forest productivity (needed people to produce 1 M m³ of roundwood) and volume of sawn timbers done per year for European and WP1 BASAJAUN partners

These two indicators allow to assess roughly the productivity in each country however one has to bear in mind that to get more realistic picture also other conditions such as species characteristics have to be taken into account. For instance, France has a lot of hardwood forest (2/3 of its forest land, more than 10 million ha), but the mechanisation level of harvesting is not the same as for softwood species as the hardwood tree diameters and heights are different.

In the next step values according to wood used in housing per countries [Hildebrandt 2017] have been modelled in order to identify the extra trees volume if wooden construction market increase (rate 0%, 10% & 20%) (Figure 3). Despite the observed dynamics, France still lags behind the leading European and North American countries:

- the incorporation rate of wood in construction has stagnated at 10% while it reached 7% for Italy, 15% in Germany, and 35% in **Northern Europe** and North America (**USA and Canada**),
- the share of wood construction over total construction is also low, individual timber-framed houses representing only 7% of houses built in 2009. In Germany, the individual timber frame houses account for 30% of built individual houses, to reach 90% in **Northern Europe** and North America. According to studies conducted by INFOR (Chile), 16.7% of total m² in homes is built with wood, and the Chilean policy want to reach 100% by 2030.

Figure 3 Expected increase in roundwood volume (1000 m3) needed if the demand of wood construction stays at its current level (0%), grows by 10% or by 20% in selected BASAJAUN partner countries (Hildebrandt 2017).

European available forest can provide wood resources to satisfy the increasing demand of wooden housing market. Today less than the initial ratio (annual production Mm3 per year /standing trees volume in Mm3) is harvested as estimated in Table 1.

Table 2. Ratio between increasing tree volume according to the wooden market under available resource in European Union

EEC - 27 countries	Wooden construction production dynamics		
	BAU*	+10%	+20%
Roundwood production volume million m ³	425 351	454 570	478 993
ratio (roundwood production volume over initial standing trees volume)	1,9%	2,06%	2,17%
Total job creation in roundwood production)	0	+23 550	+43 236
therein: estimation of female employment		+3 156	+5 794
sawn timber million m ³	98 694	104 551	110 169
Change to BAU		5,9%	11,6%
Total job creation in sawmills at rate	0	+12 051	+23 609
Therein: estimation of female employment		+2 470	+4 840

*business as usual

The European forest is in a position to meet the growing demand for timber construction. Depending on the national species available, it will always be possible to import the necessary quantities and qualities. The creation of jobs depends a lot on the industrial policy of the companies around the concept of forest and sawmill 4.0, leading to investments (CLT, canter, glulam, other engineered wood products) along the processing chain to generate added value. As mentioned above, the allocation of the right tree (so the best lumber) to the right place in the construction must optimize the transformation scheme. This can be done either by setting up a traceability system or by using tools to evaluate the resource towards the wood quality.

3. Forest Modelling in term of structural and aesthetic quality

3.1 Context

European sawmills produce typically a wide range of products answering to the heterogenous demand. Getting the right product to the right customer in a timely manner is critical. However, a growing share of the sawmills is getting more and more specialized, producing specific products, which are generally more demanding in terms of optimal log dimensions, while also additional properties, like knot sizes, strength properties, durability, surface properties, aesthetic properties, etc., may be of larger or smaller importance depending on the offered products' specification. It is important to control the timber procurement (dimensions, qualities, volumes, and schedules of incoming logs) as well as sawing process (log sorting and storage, schedules, sawing patterns, etc.) to achieve an optimal result in terms of quality and profit. In addition, the need to consider different log purchase options, market opportunities and production constraints makes it impossible to find optimum operating decisions with conventional and traditional planning methods. Consequently, there is a need for decisions support systems and technologies that facilitate accessibility to qualified information. Therefore, the best (optimal) solution must not be contradictory to processing.

The accuracy and precision of the output information from the different kind of models will be strictly depending on the quality of the input data. Furthermore, there is not “one solution fits all” for the production of all kind products. In order to understand the benefit of one blueprint “model”, we should keep in mind the wood production chain as indicated below (Table 3) and clearly identify the difficulty to link all kind of input parameters to final products.

Table 3. Forest data (Forest & Trees), common procedures and typical products along the forest to final product chain

Forest	Trees	Stems/ logs	Sawing	Materials	Final products / market
Stand Rotation age Stocking Site fertility Climate Thinning Other ...	Species Genotype Tree age Growth rate Position/height Diameter Branches (size, type, structure) Pruning	Selection Measuring Delimiting Bucking Sorting	Measuring Sorting Debarking Sawing pattern Sorting Drying Grading Peeling	Lumber Components Veneer Chips Dust Bark	Structural lumber Window frames Carpentries Decking Panels Furniture Cladding ...

3.2 Theoretical approach

For a long time, growth and yield studies have focused on the prediction of global stand and tree attributes - namely stand dominant height, basal area and volume or tree diameter at breast height (DBH) – as a function of age, stand density and site quality. These studies have led to the construction

of various types of models such as yield tables or tree distance-independent models. Connections of these models with wood quality were often limited. The only useful information that they provided about wood products were related to the size of the trees (for the mean and dominant trees with stand models or for every tree in the stand with tree models and in some cases to their taper through stem profile equations [Lanvin et al. 2008].

More recently, the need for management tools that integrate both growth and wood quality information led to a new generation of more detailed models which have mostly been developed for fast growing coniferous plantations (e.g. Douglas fir in North America and France, Radiata pine in New Zealand, Scots pine in Finland). These models operate at the tree level but may be either average tree models, distance-independent or distance-dependent tree models. One of the examples is the FORMODEL [EFORWOOD TOSIA 2008], which database is available online¹.

Although some theoretical approaches were developed already back in 1995 (Figure 4, Figure 5) only in recent years genetic aspects are beginning to be taken into account in the construction of new models (Figure 5).

Figure 4 General framework of the forest – product model used by Houllier & All [Houllier 1995]

Figure 5 Conceptual input-output exchange of 4 models developed into T4F project [T4F 2016]

To inform decision makers on sustainable forest management, ecosystem service provisioning and climate change mitigation, the four models ForGEM, ORCHIDEE, EFISCEN and ToSIA were linked. Each of these models is briefly described below and summarised in Table 3.

¹http://www.iefc.net/bdd/models/modeles_liste.php?filtre_valeur=EFORWOOD&%20filtre_champ=Context

Table 4 Overview of models

Name	Purpose
ForGEM (FOREst Genetics, Ecophysiology and Management) has been developed by the University and Research Centre, Wageningen, Netherlands	Assessment of interactions between climate change and forest management on growth, species composition, rates of adaptive response and adaptive potential of forests
ORCHIDEE is a land surface model that has been widely applied for both climate simulations and land surface simulations. Soft has been developed by CEAE (France)	Quantify the climate effects of the interactions between changing atmospheric GHG concentrations, climate change, land cover (change), and land management (including forestry).
EFISCEN European Forest Information SCENario has been developed by EFI (European Forest Institute)	Provide insight in European forest resource development, biomass availability and ecosystem service provisioning under different climate change and management scenarios
ToSIA (Tool for Sustainability Impact Assessment) by EFI (European Forest Institute) during EFORWOOD project	Provide insight in sustainability impacts on wood value chains

3.3 Tree Tools

The modelling of virtual stems may, however, vary between dynamic growth simulators, empirical regression models or CT-scanner measurements. Some existing model systems operating with virtual logs are described below.

3.3.1 SAW2003 (LTD)

Through application of tree models, stem shape and internal knot structure of Scots pine stems could be predicted using site, stand, and tree variables. Stem shape was described by stem taper and cross-sectional eccentricity. Knot properties included were knot diameter, sound knot length, loose knot length, number of knots per whorl, and longitudinal inclination. This model system was then integrated in a sawmill conversion simulation system (Saw2003) in order to evaluate lumber recovery in terms of lumber dimension distribution, volume, grade, and value [Moberg L. 2006]. These applications showed that it was possible to predict the lumber grade recovery on the basis of stand and tree measurements. When comparing results of tree models against empirical data for 604 logs, the volume recovery of side boards was overestimated with the modelling approach, but the volume recovery of centre boards and the grade recovery showed good agreement. For both methods, the recovery of the strictest grade decreased slightly with increasing diameter at breast height class but increased with increasing lumber dimension. The results of this study illustrate how the Saw2003 system can be applied to estimate the lumber volume and grade recovery of standing Scots pine trees.

3.3.2 SILVES (Inrae)

Recent developments in the modelling of tree growth and wood quality have produced new models and software packages that enable the simulation of timber properties, usually at the stand level. Separately foresters are now deeply involved in the development and implementation of GIS concerning forest yield, vegetation, soil properties, climatic variables etc. To our knowledge there is no wood quality information available in such a data base.

The objective of SYLVE (Computer simulations and visualisation software applied to silviculture) [Blaise 2002] is to demonstrate that it is possible to establish a linkage between these Growth and Wood

Quality models and the available forest geographic information. The software involved for this work are (i) AMAP that allows to simulate and to stage 3D shapes of plants including trees species , (ii) ARCINFO© a commercial GIS, (iii) IMAGIS which interfaces AMAP and GIS in order to represent GIS information in a realistic way, (iv) Win-EPIFN which simulates the board properties from one stand described by usual forest inventory measurements.

The Win-EPIFN software (primarily developed for use with Norway spruce plantations in north eastern of France) works in three steps:

1. Modelling of the past growth of each individual tree (described by age, height and diameter at breast height) in order to know the stem shape, branch pattern and internal stem wood properties.
2. Simulation of stem conversion in log and boards with their respective properties such as ring width, wood density, number and characteristics of knots (KAR, ...).
3. Simulation according to grading rules in order to provide a standard value for each product.

3.3.3 MOTTI (Luke)

MOTTI is a stand-level analysis tool and decision support system for forest management. It facilitates assessing the effects of alternative forest management practices on stand development and the profitability of forest management. The core of MOTTI is a stand-level simulator, which includes growth and yield models for e.g. natural regeneration, growth and mortality. It is designed to simulate stand development under alternative management regimes and growth conditions in Finland [Hynynen 2005]. MOTTI predicts the development of the user-defined initial stand until the end of the rotation. The user can define various management schedules including management practices, such as precommercial and commercial thinning, fertilization, and ditch network maintenance in peatland forests. The user can adjust parameters such as timing and intensity of thinning and proportions of tree species and define the timing of final cut. If the user does not define management practices, MOTTI simulates a default management program for the stand based on the current recommendations for forestry practice in Finland. For the economic analysis (net present value and bare land value), the user can enter stumpage prices by tree species and timber assortments, costs (e.g. costs of first commercial thinning, fertilisation and ditch network maintenance) and interest rate. The results will be presented in the form tables, graphs and files exportable to Excel.

3.3.4 Modelling tools synthesis

So far, models predicting wood properties are only applied to a limited degree in manufacturing of wood products. The type of sawing simulators presented in this chapter are not yet implemented to online systems but are considered useful especially for planning. In the context of BASAJAUN, the objective is to select and buck logs of suitable (economically and/or environmentally) combinations of diameter, length and wood properties to fit specific processes and products and to collect and deliver these logs to the desired production lines. This requires operational online systems, but so far only models providing cross-section and log averages have been implemented in bucking computers as shown below.

Figure 6 *Manufacturing starts in the forest. In CTL (Cut To Length) systems the selection, bucking alternatives and sorting of produced wood are all decided at harvesting (Photo Komatsu Forest)*

Figure 7 *Choose the right log to maximize yield by optimizing the entire log sorting process from X-ray systems and 3D scanners to advanced optimization software (<https://remasawco.se/logsorting/>)*

3.4 Trunk Volume versus Wood Value approach

Wood quality, as understood within academic and industrial contexts, has to do with a specific performance in relation to some preconceived application of each log or piece of wood under consideration. As quality assessment is multi-faceted and depends on the intended application, there is no absolute measure even when assessing common parameter such as wood density, knot area ratio, fibre deviation, fibre morphology, etc.

In order to allocate the proper raw material to the various process chains, various standards and grading rules have been established such as the European Standards series EN1316 and EN1927 for roundwood grading. This very complex process from lumber grading to reliable design values is still under research and improvement.

Understanding and following wood quality from one forest stand, the natural environment must be considered, which makes up a forest, and the single trees. Steered by the genetic code and the environment of a forest stand trees will grow and produce the stem over time changing wood property.

Due to the action of gravity, each portion of stem must support the weight located above. During tree growth, both the amount of supported weight and the supporting geometry are continually and simultaneously changing also accounting the maturation stage of the new cell layer.

Figure 4 provides a graphical survey on the complex interrelation of genetics, environmental factors, silviculture, wood material properties, process parameters and the material properties of the final product. There are significant possibilities to tailor and control wood properties along the whole forestry wood process chain as by tree breeding, silvicultural measures and specific technological concepts (e.g. wood modification and specific wood raw material conversion concepts).

From the wood raw material to the final product, there is a complex process chain, where the final product properties can be influenced all along the chain, right from the beginning. To optimize the

“wood quality flow” lots of information is needed and has to be exchanged forwards and backwards between the single steps of the chain.

From the wood raw material to the final product, there is a complex process chain, where the final product properties can be influenced all along the chain, right from the beginning. To optimize the “wood quality flow” lots of information is needed and has to be exchanged forwards and backwards between the single steps of the chain.

The expectations on the raw material might change over the time due to changes in technology and product development.

Due to the different morphology of a trunk there is a discrepancy between the merchantable timber volume of a tree and the value of the wood of a tree as shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 8 Relationship between volume and relatively high and internal knot distribution [Teischinger 2017]

Figure 9 Example of volume (“pourcentage du volume”) and value (“pourcentage de valeur sur pied”) of French oak. [Lemaire 2010]

This also leads to differentiated pricing on the timber market and differentiation is quite often more pronounced for hardwood than for softwood.

With just a few clicks, the MOTTI smartphone application allows you to quantify what you see in the forest, in particular standing material, tree height, basal area, number of stems per hectare and growth. The application also includes a growth model, which makes it possible to simulate the medium-term evolution of the stand in question. It allows the measured data to be synchronized with a server and downloaded back to the office in Excel format.

Screen output "stem distribution" in categories of 4 cm diameter at breast height obtained mainly on the basis of basal area and number of stems per hectare.

Figure 10 Main interface of MOTTI: measuring instruments, inventory modes and application settings [Noiret 2016]

3.5 Traceability and models

Tree, log or sawn timber model analysis shows that there are gaps between wood property information desired by the industry and wood properties possible to predict by statistical models. Part of the problem might have its origin in different ways to express wood properties along the value chains. Time are needed to fit input raw material measurement to final output data into chain as shown below.

Figure 11 Examples of interaction between models (predicted) and output data needed by industrial processing

The literature contains many research studies, but in many cases the statistics produced are descriptive, and models predicting properties are missing. However, a lot of models predicting some of the wood properties of interest for industry have been published, some of them including predefined characteristics, with a large potential to be applied in wood industries. However, the principal benefit of “Models” is that they help companies to understand their operations and to improve their profits. However, a financial analysis of costs and profits must be performed before implementation of such wood quality model. Traceability in the wood construction value chains.

According to the ISO 12875:2011 standard, traceability concerns “the ability to trace the history, application and location of that which is under consideration, and for products this can include the origin of materials and parts, the processing history and the distribution and location of the product after delivery. Traceability includes not only the principal requirement to be able to physically trace products through the distribution chain, from origin to destination and vice versa, but also to be able to provide information on what they are made of and what has happened to them”.

In other words, traceability is the ability to follow a product (or knowledge) from an origin to a destination. Traceability is carried out by means of recorded identifications defined by stakeholders involved into the implementation, which is complex. It could allow identifying the following information for a product:

- all manufacturing steps,

- the sources of its components and their suppliers,
- the places the product or its components have been stored in,
- all controls, auditing, and tests carried out for the product or its components,
- the equipment used to manufacture and handle the product,
- direct customers who purchased the product, etc.

Figure 12 Technologies to provide better traceability by UBI Solution – France <https://www.ubisolutions.net/en/>

There is a difference between traceability, logistical tracking, and life-cycle assessment approach. Product logistical tracking refers to locating a product in space and time (answered questions are: where, when?). Life-cycle assessment (LCA), on the other hand, aims at description of product's contents to provide all available information regarding the product life cycle (answered questions are: with what, why, how, by whom?).

Figure 13 Deming wheel used by Optel – Canada <https://www.optelgroup.com/fr/>

Traceability concept fulfils several functions: identification, location, authentication, and security. Identification function is used to link an item with data from databases by using a unique identifier as a key. Location function consists of a set of sensors to detect the location of an item within the production chain. Authentication function allows tackling counterfeiting with tamper proof signature. Finally, security function ensures product integrity.

In addition, a tracing system can be made up of two different components. On the one hand a documentary traceability (the written information about the product), and on the other hand a physical traceability (the identification mark on the product itself). Documentary traceability is always needed, but it is not mandatory to apply a physical mark on each item. It is possible to use references to link documents along the supply chain process (contract, orders, production tickets, shipment status and invoices, geographical origin marking, CE marking, PEFC or FSC, ...). Documentary and physical traceability are always expected to correspond with each other. Physical component is useless without documentary.

In this context, it is very important to share same understanding of the necessary level of accuracy between all stakeholders right at the beginning of BASAJAUN project. This requires, in particular, comprehensive analysis of the studied process with all production and transformation steps of products to trace.

Figure 14 Outline of a forest to final products chain (Indisputable Key)

Each point where a product either enters or exits a production or transformation location, from “BASAJAUN supply chain origin” to “BASAJAUN supply chain destination”, must be identified. These are the points at which monitoring is to be developed into WP3.

3.6 Traceability: a multi-components system

A tracing system must fulfil various functionalities, as described above.

Data acquisition requires to concurrently identify physical flows, players, locations, the documents required for item movement, the equipment used for processing, handling and transporting the flows, the activities that make up the process, and the sequence of activities. Therefore, it is based on the implementation of a coherent identification system throughout the entire process that ensures that the data tracked will have the same meaning for everyone involved. Standardization helps mutual understanding.

At each point, in which a product is bought, sold, or processed, it is necessary to collect a key to link with previous steps and to create a key to link with further steps. If a physical traceability is used, it consists of reading an identifier and marking a new one after the processing of the product.

The stored data is important for analysis and monitoring. If several stakeholders are involved, a central database is often implemented. It not only enables access to the data for all stakeholders but also facilitates the transparency needs. In order to increase the security and transparency, a blockchain may be developed. A blockchain is based on several databases maintained across several computers that are linked in a peer-to-peer network. It allows digital information distribution but no copying. Thus,

it is a distributed network. The information is constantly reconciled into the database, which is stored in multiple locations and updated instantly. That means the records are public and verifiable. Since there is no central location but the data is fragmented and located in many places, it is difficult to hack.

Without a block chain each participant in the chain has its own database accompanied by synchronization problems and update delays.

The system must be able to **process the data** to have a real picture of the activities carried out in the company and of the links between activities. The result is the creation of the performance indicators required to pilot processes and compile statistics.

The challenge for **dissemination** is to ensure continuity at the information flow level in parallel with physical flows and production activities.

Figure 15 Components of a traceability system

Besides technical aspects, human dimension shall be taken into account, which is often the most complicated point. The more stakeholders are involved, the more complex is the implementation. It is a question of trusting relationship and change management at an internal and global level.

It is also important to bear in mind that economical dimension is a key point and for instance, RFID technology struggles to take off in the forest-based sector because of its unit cost (1 € for a tree costing to 35 € (i.e., in the case of pulpwood).

The use of a blockchain allows the redundancy of update actions, reduces the need for intermediaries (see Figure 16). This network is also less vulnerable, since it uses consensus models to validate information. Transactions are thus secure, authenticated, and verifiable.

Participants in both transaction systems are the same. The change is that the recording of the transaction is shared by all parties and it is visible to everybody.

3.7 Wood traceability today: myth or reality?

3.7.1 State-of-the-art in France

It is clear that today, at least in France, there is often a gap between traceability wishes and feasibility. Hence, deployment of physical traceability is limited to small parts of a wood supply chain. Companies face technical constraints such as the difficulty to mark each item individually when there are too many items, or when transformation process of a product is too fast. Furthermore, when a technical solution could be possible, it is not often implemented due to financial constraints. Financial constraints are a considerable problem but in France, also the fear of exchanging information on one's production is another difficulty to overcome.

Figure 16 Follow-up of successive states of products with Blockchain

Figure 17 Example of traceability [FCBA private source from Arto Usenius VTT 2010]

Nevertheless, in this context, documentary traceability is well-managed and technically controlled. It is used for tracing of origin in order to ensure local wood, or to certify chain of custody related to environmental certification (PEFC, FSC). The same cannot be said for physical traceability, which is used in logistics topics (from forest to sawmill wood yard) and data modelling. It is developed in a small scale. In long log use cases, RFID tags can sometimes be used by item and with manual implementation with a marking hammer. However, in short logs (100% of logs, e.g., in Aquitaine region) bar codes are used in piles instead of RFID tags.

Many R&I projects have been carried out at a national or European level to help specification and implementation of traceability systems in the wood supply chain (e.g., Lineset (QLK5-CT-1999-01467 FP5-LIFE QUALITY), IndisputableKey (N° 034732 FP6-IST), ...). Eventually, in the scope of log by log physical traceability, many prototypes were developed, many use cases were documented, but few have been really deployed.

The definition of a traceability system must therefore take into consideration, on the one hand, the relationship between the goal pursued and the effectiveness sought, and, on the other hand, the cost of implementation compared to the product's specific/available cost margin. The result is an equilibrium between different requirements and, in particular, the demands of customers and consumers: the propensity of the consumer to pay to "know more".

3.7.2 BASAJAUN wood supply chain

The aim of this section is to describe a potential BASAJAUN traceability tool to improve wood supply chain in a French context in order to sell 1,000 m³ of C24 grade sawn timber (or G4 1-2 if required quality is an aesthetic one).

In a classical way, this would mean to provide a certain number of trees in the forest to grow and to take a long time to sell sawmill products at the end of the value chain. A new path could be the analysis of wood transformation processes by an inverse methodology applying traceability tools. For a sawn

cubic meter with a defined quality, sawmills should know the type of logs, stems and forests. All wood research done at FCBA to characterise species follow this concept: data from forests to products were collected, validated, stored and processed in modelling. (Annex 1 describes France' traceability protocol).

As a part of the analyses (forests, logs, sawing, intrinsic quality of products) concerning maritime pine, the following figure shows the interest of such an approach in increasing profits and reducing production time. In order to calculate the gain, the case of a sawmill producing 500 m³/days, which has an order for 1000 m³ of ST II-C24 for a specific market has been used. The estimated costs of stems (purchase price at 30 – 60 €/m³) and sawn timber (resale price at 200-250 €/m³ wet wood) to carpentry market (400 – 450 €/m³) were applied.

The benefits (time/day of production) are derived from scenario 1 (purchased trees without regulation) and scenario 2 (buy only trees able to inherit high roundwood quality) and presented in the following figure along with the days of production to complete the 1000 m³ order.

Figure 18 Example of ROI from traceability on maritime pine [FCBA private source].

It can be observed that sawmills should purchase specific trees in order to make the highest possible benefit. In this scenario (1,000 m³) the highest benefit generated is estimated at 13,000 €, the manufacturing time is decreased by 16%. Although traceability generates costs (equipment, data recording time, data analysis), they are quickly recouped in shorter production time and financial gains.

The above scheme follows not only the Halco WOODMAN™ System, which is designed for any combination of harvesting operations, log purchases, and sales for, e.g., sawmills, but also modelling traceability in the forestry-wood supply chain [Sirkka 2008].

Woodman Viewer - C:\Projects\SGDI\Woodman_V2-9-0\OutputFiles\printTestBuck01

Trees	TreesNum=31	TreeID	TreeCode	Species	SpType	DBH	Height	StumpH	BuckDia	WF	QFI	Cf
11	Salgher_CARL	B.072501	DougFr	DougFr	DF	17.100	102.000	0.500	16.6	0.5	0.7	
32	Salgher_CARL	B.072502	DougFr	DougFr	DF	9.8	99.5	0.5	9.9	1.6	0.2	
33	Salgher_CARL	B.072503	DougFr	DougFr	DF	18.9	94.5	0.5	18.9	0.4	0.8	

Stems	StemsNum=31	StemID	TreeCode	TypeCode	Length	ButtDia	ButtDia	TopDia	SlpMethod	WF	Medium	SegStemNum
1	31	0	Mixed	0.000	167.000	0.000	16.6	0.4	DF_0_V	0.5	32	32

Logs	LogsNum=65	LogID	StemCode	SortCode	Length	ButtDia	BuckDia	TopDia	Taper	LbMethod	MI	WF
65	31	MPGenDag	Sawlog		41.000	0.000	16.6	12.6	0.100	KGes	GenDM	108.3
66	31	BDPGenPr	Peeler		35.000	41.000	12.6	7.3	0.164	EPeeler	GenMtr	108.3
67	31		LengthReject		6.000	76.000	7.3	6.0	0.212			108.3

Blocks	BlocksNum=242	BlockID	LogID	SortCode	MainLen	Length	ButtDia	ButtDia	TopDia	Taper	DcyFrac	BlkGr	Grade	WF	BlkValue
243	65	bcSawlogS	Sawlog		20	20.750	20.250	14.7	12.6	0.106	0.000	AKR	1	97.4	0.000
244	65	bcSawlogS	Sawlog		10	10.250	0.000	16.6	15.6	0.100	0.000	AKR	1	5.4	0.000

Dimension Cant Breakdown

Figure 19 WOODMAN™ business model for operations-wide optimization of forest products operations, from the forest to the finished product <http://www.halcosoftware.com/software-5-woodman>

The following part of this report describes how can traceability could be done step by step.

The initial proposed scheme for the traceability in BASAJAUN project considers the following processes:

- harvesting process (Figure 20)
- log yard process (Figure 21)
- primary wood processing process (Figure 22)
- secondary wood processing process (Figure 23)

If it is not possible to measure automatically some parameters, especially during felling (measuring by the harvester head not implemented yet), a measurement by the operator could be possible, and mean value could be used, too.

For logistics purpose, it is possible to track each stem during the forwarding process and the transport process. In this case, a reading of each stem mark is needed during each process.

Process	Wood type	Type of traceability			Data to be measured or recovered from a database or read
		Create a physical mark	By Item or By Batch	Need a reading	
1	Management	No	By stand	No	Localization (stand ID), Mean Age (years) of stand, Mean Density (Trees/ha) of stand, mean Height (m) of trees, mean DBH (cm) of stand
					Standing trees
2	Felling	Yes ID-L1	By item	No	Localization (stand ID), • by increment ID-L1, Stem length with top diam at 7cm (m), Age (years), Height (m), DbH (cm), Internode length, EN1927 grade (A B C D), height of first live knot (m), height of first dead knot (m)
					Stems in Forest
3	Forwarding	No	By item	No (Yes if needed for logistics management ID-L1)	(ID-L1)
					Stems at road side
4	Transport	No	By item	No (Yes if needed for logistics management ID-L1)	(ID-L1)
					Stems at wood yard

Figure 20 Harvesting traceability processes (In red, missing data which should be included at the end of the project. In blue, necessary data for modelling, in green, commercial data)

Process	Wood type	Type of traceability			Data to be measured or recovered from a database or read
		Create a physical mark	By Item or By Batch	Need a reading	
5	Wood reception	No	By item	Yes ID-L1	ID-L1
					Stems at log yard
6	Measurement	No	By item	Yes ID-L1	ID-L1, Heartwood diameter (mm), Maximum knot diameter at surface (mm),
					Stems at log yard
7	Cut to length / Sorting	Yes ID-L2	By item	No	ID-L1, ID-L2, Length, volume Log position in stem, distance from pitch (cm), Heartwood diameter (mm)
					Logs at log yard
8	Debarking	No	By item	No	
					Logs at log yard

Figure 21 Log yard traceability processes (In red, missing data which should be included at the end of the project. In blue, necessary data for modelling, in green, commercial data)

Process	Wood type	Type of traceability			Data to be measured or recovered from a database or read
		Create a physical mark	By Item or By Batch	Need a reading	
9	1st sawing Lumbers	Yes ID-L3	By item	Yes ID-L2	ID-L2, ID-L3
10	2nd sawing Lumbers	Yes ID-L4	By item	Yes ID-L3	ID-L3, ID-L4, NTD measurement Edyn, Knottiness, Knottiness grade on 2 (G2) or 4 faces (G4)
11	Cut to length Lumbers	Yes ID-L5	By item	Yes ID-L4	ID-L4, ID-L5
12	Sorting Lumbers	Yes ID-L6	By item	Yes ID-L5	ID-L5, ID-L6 Grade (CE marking)
13	Planing Lumbers	Yes ID-L7	By item	Yes ID-L6	ID-L6, ID-L7
14	Stacking Stack of lumbers	Yes ID-L8	By batch	Yes ID-L7	ID-L8, ID-L7 Volume

Figure 22 Sawmill traceability processes (In red, missing data which should be included at the end of the project. In blue, necessary data for modelling, in green, commercial data)

Process	Wood type	Type of traceability			Data to be measured or recovered from a database or read
		Create a physical mark	By Item or By Batch	Need a reading	
15	Storage Stacks of lumbers	No	By batch	Yes ID-L7	ID-L8
16	Drying Stacks of lumbers	No	By batch	Yes ID-L8	ID-L8
17	Preservation Stacks of lumbers	No	By batch	Yes ID-L8	ID-L8
18	Storage Stacks of lumbers	No	By batch	Yes ID-L8	ID-L8
19	Shipment Stacks of lumbers	Yes ID-L9	By batch	Yes ID-L8	ID-L8, ID-L9

Figure 23 Second transformation traceability processes (In red, missing data which should be included at the end of the project. In blue, necessary data for modelling, in green, commercial data).

Other process to the Basajaun wood supply destination should be added with WP4 products and WP5 regulation to improve collecting data and real time of analysis.

3.8 Conclusions of traceability

Traceability offers two major advantages to wood companies:

- To know the position and the quality of the products at real time
- To increase benefits (reduce time of production and purchase best raw material) from data inverse statistical analysis.

Depending on the traceability system specifications required by the BASAJAUN project, it is possible to implement the temporal data model define by Sirkka (2008) to support tracking of the raw material and monitoring of the processes.

Because the performance of the supply chain depends strongly on the performance of each business entity, a real-time traceability solution can help optimising the allocation of the best raw material for the best performance in the final (wood-based construction) product.

Figure 24 Traceability: allocation of optimal raw material for the production process.

4. Conclusions

The forestry-wood sector is important for employment and for sustaining green areas. Forests cover 2/5 of the European surface area. Wood is a natural and renewable resource, wood industry is committed to developing in accordance with the rules of sustainable forest management schemes. Wood meets has many applications in different sectors of the economy (construction, development, packaging and logistics, energy, paper, textiles, etc.). The use of wood, in all its various forms, makes it possible to store carbon (1m³ of wood = 1 ton of sequestered CO₂), and as a fuel at the end of life of a wooden product, it limits the use of fossil energy sources. It is important to know that a building made with a high proportion of wood has a lower impact on the environment: less exhaustible raw materials are used, and less energy is consumed in its manufacturing and constructing process.

The volume of forest biomass that can be sustainably mobilised is largely satisfactory to meet the increasing demand of using wood in construction. This analysis was based on simplified assumptions, however, and it does not take into account e.g. the challenges of insect attacks and/or fires or even drought periods. Forest management plans can be adapted to increase the supply while maintaining healthy and resilient ecosystems.

It must be noted that it is difficult to estimate the quality of standing trees. At the present stage, for the use in operational logging, comparatively simple and robust regression models (including mixed models), not depending on non-gatherable input data, shall be preferred. However, available tools are complex, not enough tailor-made to be considered as embedded systems. Moreover, the margin of error may remain high in some models.

At this stage, the influence quantities (less than ten parameters) are listed, only the analysis of the yield (quality and quantity) will allow to identify the biases by means of a chain of traceability. This task has to be tackled by WP3 partners.

BASAJAUN project is a new chance for sawmill industry to take into account new technologies in order to better assess customer needs. It should be based on available raw material resources. Thus, it will increase benefits when ordered products quality is specified more precisely.

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6. Annex 1 - France traceability protocol

For more than 20 years, FCBA has been conducting qualification campaigns for French wood (hardwood and softwood) in order to characterize the species for structural use. Qualification campaigns consist of identification and assessment of all characteristics that describe and influence wood quality and wood mechanical properties and performances. The gathering of the boards is done through by the selection of the representative trees in forest with an operational but not industrial traceability. However, this minimalist traceability allows us to "predict" the intrinsic quality of the trees by reverse analysis. This step considerably increases the time of the study, but it allows us to acquire a large amount of information.

6.1 Measurements of features on stand

Measurement on stand	Nb of digit	Example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Localization 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mean age of the trees if known (Years) 	3	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actual stand density if known (trees/Ha) 	4	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actual stand mean if known height (m) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actual stand mean if known DBH (cm) 	2	

In yellow, missing data which should be included at the end. In blue, data for modeling

6.2 Measurements on standing tree

Measurement on standing tree	NB of digit	Example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age (years) 	3	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DBH (cm) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tree height (m) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Height of the dead branch if known (m) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Height of the green branch if known (m) 	2	

In yellow, missing data which should be included at the end. In blue, data for modeling

6.3 Measurements of features on felled tree during harvesting time

Measurement on ground	Nb of digit	Example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> height of first live knot if known (m) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> height of first dead knot if known (m) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> length of stem with top diameter of 7 cm (m) 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internode length 	2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EN 1927 grade (A, B, C, D) 	1 (text)	

In yellow, missing data which should be included at the end. In blue, data for modeling

6.4 Measurements on stem in sawmill or forest during harvesting time

Measurement on stem	Nb of digit	Example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EN 1927 grade (A, B, C, D) Heartwood diameter (mm) 	1 (text) 2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum knot diameter at surface (mm) 	2	

In yellow, missing data which should be included at the end. In blue, data for modeling

6.5 Measurements on log in sawmill

Measurement on log	Nb of digit	Example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cut to length according to size of specimens tested (top diameter < 20 cm) 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of Log position in stem 		One colour by height
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of distance from pith in cm 	P1	identification by color system P1 = 20mm ; P2 = 40 mm
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Juvenile wood 	2	Diameter

6.6 Measurements on lumber in sawmill

NDT Tools (if possible)	Nb of digit	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NDT measurement Edyn 	C - 2 D - 2	CE marking EN 14081-1 - strength assessment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knottiness 	C - 2 digits D - 2 digits	CE marking EN 14081-1 - strength assessment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knottiness grade (0, 1, 2, 3, 4) on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> two faces (G2) or four faces (G4) 	G2-1 digit G4-1 digit	Aesthetic assessment EN1611-1 (softwood)

Basajaun is a European innovation action about sustainable building with wood. The main objective is to demonstrate how wood construction chains can be optimized to foster both rural development and urban transformation whilst being connected with sustainable forest management in Europe. The consortium comprises 29 partners from 12 countries including 8 leading research and technology organizations, 3 universities, 15 companies and 4 other public and sectoral organizations. The project is coordinated by the Tecnalia Research and Innovation Foundation in Spain.

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